

Assessing the Impact of Entrepreneurship Training On Business Performance: A Case Study of Small-Scale Trained Entrepreneurs in Maseru

Author's Details:

(1) Francis Okyere (Ph.D.) (2) Tankiso Makara

Department of Business and Management Development-National University of Lesotho

Abstract

Empirical evidence suggests that a large number of factors contribute to small firm success. Entrepreneurship Education/Training (ET) has been cited as one of the most important factors that impact business performance. In Lesotho, there are several organisations that offer ET to potential and established entrepreneurs. However, empirical research of such training on the impact of business success is limited. The purpose of this study was to examine the influence of ET on the business performance of small-scale entrepreneurs in Maseru, the capital of Lesotho. The study rested in the interpretivist epistemology in the subjective ontology of conducting social research. Therefore, a qualitative research approach was employed with an open-ended questionnaire to collect data from 20 entrepreneurs in Maseru. One key finding that emerged in the empirical study was that ET has a positive impact on firm performance. On the other hand, the study participants identified a lack of financial assistance, high rent, and lack of access to international markets among others as factors constraining their efforts. Based on these findings, the study makes recommendations to policymakers, ET providers and donor agencies on what support mechanisms to put in place to support entrepreneurs so as to ensure sustainable economic growth

Keywords: *entrepreneurship, entrepreneur, entrepreneurship training, business performance*

1. Introduction

Governments across the world are increasingly recognizing the positive impact that the creation of new businesses can have on employment levels, as well as the competitive advantages that small firms can bring to the market place (Scase, 2007). Therefore, the important role played by entrepreneurs in socio-economic development cannot be overemphasized. In developing countries, such as Lesotho, entrepreneurs are recognised as drivers of economic development, in terms of employment creation, poverty alleviation, import reduction, among others. The key to Lesotho's economic growth and strength is in the development of entrepreneurship. It is now well recognized that education and training opportunities play a key role in cultivating future entrepreneurs and in developing the abilities of existing entrepreneurs to grow their businesses to greater levels of success (Henry, Hill & Leitch, 2005). The instability of markets in recent years resulted in the demise of mass production, and failure of more businesses because entrepreneurs lack entrepreneurial skills and knowledge, according to Thurik and Weneekers (2006). Entrepreneurship education and training have grown tremendously in recent years, and this growth is witnessed in the number of entrepreneurship colleges and universities in countries all around the globe. The European Commission (2008) contend that the aim of entrepreneurship education and training should be to develop entrepreneurial capacities and mindsets that benefit economies by fostering creativity, innovation, and self-employment. It is thus safe to state that all new businesses require a certain amount of entrepreneurial skill.

Nwangwu (2007) states that the failure of tertiary education to inculcate entrepreneurship training in students has led to wastages in terms of both human and natural resources. The Bacha Entrepreneurship Project Training (BEPT) (2017) in conjunction with the Central Bank of Lesotho (CBL) report that of the estimated 7,500 graduates who enter the job market every year in Lesotho, over half do not get jobs. This picture becomes gloomier when one looks at the current unemployment rate in the country which is at 27.2% (World Data Atlas, 2017). Ayodele (2006) in Arogundade (2011) suggests that the high rate of graduate and/or youth unemployment can be attributed to include irrelevant education that is bookish, theoretic and white-collar jobs oriented. Kithae et al. (2013) opine that a well-trained entrepreneur will portray most of the entrepreneurial traits, and these will then be translated into business growth. It is against this backdrop that Basotho Enterprises

Development Corporation (BEDCO), in partnership with Lesotho Revenue Authority (LRA) and Standard Lesotho Bank (SLB) have joined efforts to assist young unemployed graduates between the ages of 21 and 35 to become employers and drivers of economic growth by becoming entrepreneurs in a project called Bacha Entrepreneurship Project (BEP). Aside from that, there are two other institutions of higher learning (Institute of Extra Mural Studies of the National University of Lesotho and Limkokwing University of Creative Technology) that offer degree programmes in entrepreneurship.

Assessing the impact of ET on firm performance of small-scale entrepreneurs is very important. It is the only tool that ET providers, donors, and governments can use to indicate the effectiveness of their programmes. Afrane (2002) postulate that impact assessment generally, is aimed at measuring the effect of development projects on the intended beneficiaries. Thus, the rationale is to ascertain whether the resources invested produce the level of output and benefits as well as contribute to the mission of the organisation that makes the investment. The problem is that in the absence of systematic and empirical research, it will be difficult to determine how entrepreneurs who receive training go about their business activities and how such training impacts on business performance or success. There is, therefore, the need to embark on research so as to inform policymakers and entrepreneurship education/training providers what appropriate measures to put in place to enhance the promotion of entrepreneurship, particularly in Lesotho. This study is intended to fill that gap by assessing the link between entrepreneurship education/training and business performance of small-scale entrepreneurs in Lesotho. In this study, the term entrepreneurship training (ET) will mean any entrepreneur who has received some form of entrepreneurship training or education.

2. Literature review

2.1 What is entrepreneurship?

The meaning of entrepreneurship has evolved ever since it was first established in the 1700s. According to Williams and Nadin (2013), research regarding entrepreneurship has been a challenge given the absence of a consistent definition of the term among scholars. Herbert and Link (2011), Lucky and Olusegun (2012), Bula (2013) and Okyere (2017) contend that prior studies have identified a number of core goals that can be considered in defining entrepreneurship, namely: to define entrepreneurship as a creative business whose fundamental purpose is to create value by innovatively bringing together resources to exploit opportunities for the purpose of wealth creation. Pender (2009) argues that depending on what intellectual tradition we follow, entrepreneurship either enhances the allocative efficiency for given ends and means or drives the dynamic performance of the system through the progressive creation of new products, processes or markets. Below are some extant definitions of entrepreneurship.

Nieman et al. (2003) believe entrepreneurship is the process that causes changes in the economic system through innovations of individuals who respond to opportunities in the market. In the process, entrepreneurs create values for themselves and society. Panda (2011) is of the view that entrepreneurship is the design of a business idea, and the projection and maintenance of the organisation so that the activity may continue to take place. Rusu et al. (2012) see entrepreneurship as the ability of an individual to put into practice an idea, and the possession of certain qualities such as creativity, innovation, risk taking, and ability to plan and manage the activities in view of fulfilling the proposed goals. Pahuja and Sanjeev (2015) contend entrepreneurship can be summed up as nothing but the process of creating something new with value, particularly responding to the opportunities available. It involves time, efforts and assumption of risk, with the expectation of receiving the rewards at the end. The rewards can take any form- monetary or non-monetary. For the purpose of this study, entrepreneurship is defined as the process whereby a person uses his or her creativity and innovation to establish a business because he/she sees an opportunity and manages the business with the aim of making a profit while acknowledging the risks involved (Okyere, 2016; 2017).

The review on the definition of entrepreneurship above has portrayed the concept as a combination of three elements, namely, (i) the context in which the opportunity arises and/or is created, (ii) a set of personal abilities

necessary to identify and use that opportunity, and (iii) the capacity to materialize the opportunity, by transforming it into results.

The following key elements have also been revealed in the concept: innovation, creativity, risk taking, recognition of opportunity in the market, the establishment of a new enterprise, managing the enterprise, creation of value in society, growing the enterprise, and creation of employment (Okyere, 2016; 2017). In developing countries such as Lesotho, with high unemployment, retrenchment and inequality, creativity, innovation, and management resources can promote self-employment and good business practices so as to minimize these socio-economic problems.

2.2 Who is an entrepreneur?

In spite of the numerous publications on entrepreneurship, no generally accepted definition of the entrepreneur has emerged. A literature search reveals that contributions to the definition of the entrepreneur have come from agriculture, anthropology, economics, education, finance, history, marketing, mass communication, political science, psychology, sociology and strategic management (Okyere, 2016). The following explores various definitions of the entrepreneur and establishes an operational definition of the concept for the purpose of this study.

Cantillon (1755, cited in Bula 2012) was the first economist to acknowledge the entrepreneur as a key economic factor, and that entrepreneurs make production decisions in conditions of uncertainty, thus taking on risk for which, if successful, a return is earned. Cantillon defines an entrepreneur as “an individual that equilibrates supply and demand in the economy and in this function bears risk and uncertainty”.

To Richards (1999), an entrepreneur is one who possesses the high capability of imagination, flexibility, creativity, and innovation; one willing to think conceptually and to seek change and opportunity. The entrepreneur has a high tolerance of risk and dogged optimism about the world and the eventual right to succeed in it. According to Nieman et al. (2003), an entrepreneur is a person who sees an opportunity in the market, gathers resources and create and grows a business venture to meet these needs. He or she bears the risk of the venture and is rewarded with a profit if it succeeds.

Van Aardt et al. (2011) are of the view that an entrepreneur should be seen as a person who initiates, creates, builds, expands, and sustains a venture. He/she gathers the necessary resources to exploit an opportunity in the marketplace for long-term wealth and capital gain. Therefore, for the purpose of this study, an entrepreneur is operationally defined as a person who is creative and innovative, establishes a business because there is an opportunity, and manages the business while assuming its related risks and rewards (Okyere, 2016; 2017). The following also emerged as key characteristics associated with the entrepreneur: creativity, innovative, risk-taker, dedication, determination, flexibility, and leadership.

In conclusion, the term entrepreneur has come to be used to describe persons who establish their own business. The process involved is called entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is the outcome of complex socio-economic, psychological and other factors. The entrepreneur is the key individual central to entrepreneurship who makes factors happen. The entrepreneur is the actor and entrepreneurship is the act.

2.3 Entrepreneurship training

The past few decades have seen various intervention measures devised by policymakers, NGOs and donor agencies for small businesses. Prominent among them is entrepreneurship training, which is seen as a tool to equip small business owners in order to enhance their business operations for growth and sustainability.

Entrepreneurship training has been touted as a way of acquainting entrepreneurs with working and business life skills in order to manage their ventures effectively. ET has grown significantly in many countries across the globe, and it is seen as a means of equipping people to develop entrepreneurial skills, attitudes, and behaviour. Education Centre Online (2012) states that ET is designed to teach skills and knowledge one needs to know

before embarking on a new business venture. The same source further contends that the ET process provides individuals with the concepts and skills to recognise opportunities that others have overlooked, and to have the insight, self-esteem, and knowledge to act where others have hesitated. Tambwe (2015) says ET is a business training that includes starting, improving, managing and developing businesses as well as acquiring entrepreneurial skills.

The purpose of entrepreneurship training, therefore, is to equip students with knowledge, skills, and motivation to encourage entrepreneurial success in various settings. It is hoped that at the end of entrepreneurship training students will be able to establish own business, create employment rather than seeking employment.

2.4 Business performance

Okyere (2017) observes that the terms organizational performance, business performance, firm performance, and business success have been used interchangeably by various authors in their studies. Mgeni (2015), in a review of the terms mentioned above, concluded that all of them mean the same thing. Richard et al. (2009) posit that in spite of the relevance of business performance, the concept has suffered from a lack of consensus and selection indicators. However, Walker and Brown (2004) suggest that small business success can be measured by financial and non-financial criteria although the former has been given attention in the literature. Koontz and Donnell (1993) refer to business success as the ability of an enterprise to achieve such objectives as high profit, quality product, large market shares, good financial results, and survival at a pre-determined time using relevant strategies for action. Forsaith and Hill (2000) in Walker and Brown (2004) measure business success based on either employee numbers or financial performance, such as profit, turnover or return on investment. In the mist of this inconsistencies in business success factors, Richard et al. (2009) advise that if several dimensions exist, a researcher should choose the most relevant to his or her research and judge the outcomes of this choice. For the purpose of this research, business performance indicators by Venkatraman and Ramanujam (1986) is adopted. The author's used financial indicators like profitability, return on investment, return on assets and non-financial indicators like customer satisfaction, quality, innovation, employee satisfaction, and reputation.

2.5 Impact of entrepreneurship training on business performance

Prior studies on ET on business success suggest that a large number of factors contribute to business performance or success. A study by Bradford (2007) reported that the most desired skills needed for business performance were keeping business records, market business products, and communication skills. The study concluded that ET is crucial to business performance. Tambwe's (2015) study on the impact of ET on SMEs performance showed that 72 percent of the participants indicated that the lack of ET was one of the main factors that hindered their business performance. However, the situation changed after ET was offered. 80 percent of the participants stated improved business due to the training offered, which focused among others recording keeping, customer care, costing, budgeting. In another study by Kithae (2013), the author reported that most beneficiaries of ET stated that the training programme helps them very much in calculating their profits, keeping business records, as well as distinguishing business resources from personal resources.

2.6 Entrepreneurship training programmes in Lesotho

The Lesotho government also recognizes the significance of the small business sector as one of the key areas contributing towards employment creation and economic growth against the backdrop of rising unemployment (which is estimated around 40%) and poverty. Several support mechanisms are also in place to assist small, medium and micro enterprises (SMMEs) in Lesotho. Prominent among them is the Basotho Enterprise Development Corporation (BEDCO) whose main objective is to contribute to the economic development of Lesotho by assisting small and medium-sized Basotho enterprises to develop entrepreneurship, business, and management capabilities in an efficient way. BEDCO hopes to achieve this through the training of entrepreneurs in management and technical skills; assisting entrepreneurs with the preparation of bankable

projects; assisting with the preparation of business plans; offering counseling and administering credit-services, to mention but a few (Okyere, 2016).

BEDCO in partnership with LRA and SLB have joined efforts to assist young unemployed graduates between the ages of 21 and 35 to become employers and drivers of economic growth by becoming entrepreneurs in a project called Bacha Entrepreneurship Project (BEP). According to BEPT (2017), the aim of the ET programme is to build a crop of young entrepreneurs who can break the barriers to become job creators, rather than job seekers. Also, there are two other institutions of higher learning, Institute of Extra Mural Studies of the National University of Lesotho (NUL) and Limkokwing University of Creative Technology (LUCT) that offer degree programmes in entrepreneurship. These are typically formal entrepreneurship education courses. However, these two universities do not offer short-term ET programmes for established and/or potential entrepreneurs who may need such training to either improve their existing business activities or establish new business ventures.

3. Research methodology

3.1 Philosophical approach and research design

This was a case study because it assessed small-scale entrepreneurs in Maseru who have received entrepreneurship training, and how such training impacts on business success. The literature review showed a dearth of related previous studies in Lesotho. The study was underpinned in the interpretivist epistemology in the subjective ontology of conducting social research. Therefore, a qualitative research approach was employed in line with the interpretivist research paradigm.

3.2 Population, sampling, data collection and analysis

A population or universe is the entire or complete collection, group or set of observations of interest to the researcher of a study (Cooper & Schindler, 2008). The target population for this study comprised typical small-sized entrepreneurs who have received ET by either BEDCO, BEPT, NUL or LUCT or any other training provider(s) and are managing their business ventures in Maseru. The initial idea was to select at least five beneficiaries of entrepreneurship training from BEDCO, BEPT, NUL, and LUCT. However, various attempts to get a list of entrepreneurs who had received training by BEDCO or BEPT failed. So the study focused on only graduates from NUL and LUCT. The study employed a purposive sampling technique to select 20 small-scale entrepreneurs. A researcher employs purposive sampling when he or she has something in mind and participants that suit the purpose of the study are included (Palys, 2008). A deliberate choice of participants who have received entrepreneurship training was done in line with Etiken et al. (2016) assertion that participants are chosen due to the qualities they possess. The selection might not have been exhaustive but the study was limited by budgetary and time constraints, and it was hence impossible to widen the scope.

In conformance with the qualitative approach, the measuring instrument was an unstructured questionnaire administered via interview. Thematic analysis technique was adopted to analyse data that were collected. This method was used because of its flexibility, and it also allows for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within data (Zikmund & Babin, 2010).

3.3 Results and discussion

The study assessed the impact of entrepreneurship training on business performance of small-scale entrepreneurs in Maseru. As stated in the previous section, the study employed a qualitative approach and relied on the unstructured questionnaire. The questionnaire was divided into two main sections, A and B. Section A was on the demographic characteristics of respondents. Section B assessed the impact of entrepreneurship training on business performance of small-scale entrepreneurs in Maseru. The following emerged as responses from the study participants.

3.4 Section A

3.4.1 Demographic information of respondents

Out of the twenty entrepreneurs interviewed, twelve were male while eight were female. They are all graduates who studied Entrepreneurship at the National University of Lesotho and Limkokwing University of Creative Technology. Also, all of them trade in the informal sector as micro or small enterprise owners and are between the ages of 28-44. This finding is a positive sign in the right direction, as it can be deduced that the youth are addressing their own unemployment challenges by establishing their own businesses. Again, this could mean that Entrepreneurship Education is yielding dividends, as some, if not many, of such graduates do not rely on white collar jobs but establish their own businesses. The respondents' businesses are between the ages of two to seven years old. Some of them started their businesses even before enrolling for entrepreneurship programmes at the two universities. The small-scale entrepreneurs are engaged in retail, clothing manufacturing, plastic manufacturing, poultry, and catering.

3.5 Section B

3.5.1 Impact of entrepreneurship training on business performance of small-scale entrepreneurs

The questionnaire focused on the following: (i) Key entrepreneurship skills learned from entrepreneurship education/training; (ii) challenges facing entrepreneurs; (iii) other institutions engaged in supporting entrepreneurs; and (iv) the impact of entrepreneurship training on business success. The following reports on the responses from the study participants:

Key entrepreneurship skills learned from entrepreneurship education/training

Trained entrepreneurs admitted that they have learned among others the following skills:

- **Management skills**

These are skills which are very important in the day-to-day operations of the business. The skills help in the hiring of employees, in taking disciplinary measures, and also in job rotation which could improve the value of the business if professionally practiced.

- **Marketing skills**

The skills help them in identifying business opportunities, designing a good product or service demanded by potential customers, pricing and positioning the products or services, approaching and attracting customers, learning from the competition, and practicing good customer care.

- **Financial skills**

These skills help entrepreneurs in managing business inventories, cash, payments, collections, identify profits and costs.

The findings are in line with other studies in the entrepreneurship literature. For instance, Olomi, (2006), Marimala, (2006), Bradford (2007), National Endowment for Science, Technology and Art (NESTA) (2008), and Kutzhanova, Lyons and Lichtenstein (2009) all cited financial, marketing and communication skills, management skills, and technical skills as key areas to be taught to entrepreneurship students.

Challenges facing entrepreneurs

Several challenges are faced by many entrepreneurs in the business field. However, entrepreneurs in Maseru identified the following challenges:

- Difficulty in obtaining initial start-up capital.
- Lack of access to finance to expand business ventures. This actually affects business growth.
- Lack of regular training from supportive institutions or government after completing school.
- Employees' unbecoming attitude towards customers, especially in the absence of managers/supervisors.
- Poor customer/employee relationship has a negative impact on firm performance.

- Sometimes customers delay settling their payments which reduce the rate of stock turnover which in turn reduces income. This affects the day-to-day running of the business.
- Difficulties in accessing international markets due to high competition.
- High rent, which makes it difficult to keep business in operation for long.

These views of the respondents also collaborate with what other authors say in entrepreneurship literature in relation to lack of regular entrepreneurship training after completing school to help entrepreneurs to face the real business world. Chiang and Yan (2011) also contend that because so many businesses fail within the first five years, the assumption is that the skills or characteristics for creating a business are not the same as those required to maintain a business. Kaijage (2013) also explained that the lack of regular entrepreneurship training may lead to poor management skills, financial distress, and failure.

Findings from entrepreneurs in Maseru also agree with what Stripeikis (2008) and Zuperka (2010) together with Mauchi, Mutengezanwa and Damiyano (2014) reported in their studies. The authors summarized entrepreneurs' challenges, among others, as being; absence of initial capital, the burden of legal, governmental and administrative requirements, the problem in finding suitable employees and insufficient knowledge, abilities, and experience on how to start and run the business.

Supportive institutions

Findings show that sometimes the Government of Lesotho support entrepreneurs by offering free workshops where they are equipped with skills and knowledge on how to run own businesses and maximize profits with minimum resources, and also on how to apply technical skills to enhance business operations. Different pieces of training were offered by different ministries with different departments. These include the Department of Science and Technology (under Technology and Innovation), Ministry of Education, in conjunction with Irish Aid and Ministry of Small Business.

Some of the entrepreneurs stated that after completing school, they also acquire training from different organizations (though not regular) such as; Basotho Enterprises Development Corporation (BEDCO), International Labour Organizations, United Nations Development Program (UNDP) and Lesotho National Farmers Union (LENAFU). Lesotho Revenue Authority (LRA) also acts as a source of training through temporary jobs it offers regularly to graduates to gain more skills on fieldwork and do practical activities on managerial skills, business records, reports and also computer literacy. Again, to learn to develop strategies to overcome any challenge among the business activities.

Impact of entrepreneurship education/training on business success

Findings from the study revealed that 10 out of 20 respondents already had businesses before training though their businesses were not growing because of lack of appropriate entrepreneurial skills and knowledge. However, they admitted that their businesses improved after graduating. The rest opened their businesses after graduating. They said they were initially looking for white collar jobs but when that failed, they decided to put their knowledge in entrepreneurship into self-employment. All the respondents agreed that their entrepreneurship training background has contributed tremendously towards the success of their businesses. They reported that they are now able to run their businesses professionally.

The respondents reported that their entrepreneurship training has assisted them in improving the following areas of their business practices:

- Proper and effective record keeping of business transactions which include records on purchases, sales, and creditors and debtors.
- Improved customer care and service which has increased the level of income due to an increase in customers.

- Proper planning of income and expenditure (budget).
- Good pricing of goods and services in relation to profit.
- Accessibility of markets due to proper advertising.
- The setting of the mission, vision statements and ability to manage time.
- Able to assess both internal and external business environment to stay competitive.
- Conduct prompt applied research to deal with issues that need immediate attention, without engaging the services of consultants.

The empirical findings above support the assertions by Bradford (2007) and Tambwe (2018) who concluded in their studies that entrepreneurship training enhances entrepreneurs' management skills, improves customer relations and equips entrepreneurs with proper planning and budgeting, among others. Bradford (2007) suggests that in order for entrepreneurs to have effective performance, they need training and skills related to keeping and interpreting financial records, products promotion and improve capacity to produce more output and be competitive.

3.6 Conclusions and recommendations

This study covered the findings gathered by the researcher from the identified sample group of small-scale entrepreneurs in Maseru. The qualitative research approach was adopted and purposive sampling was employed. The findings indicated that regardless of the numerous challenges faced by trained entrepreneurs, there is a positive link between entrepreneurship education/training and business success.

Based on the study findings, it is recommended that, due to the positive relationship between entrepreneurship training and business success, it is important for the government and other relevant organizations to provide regular entrepreneurship training to entrepreneurs. This should serve as one of the strategies of enhancing their management capabilities for them to excel and have a competitive advantage in enhancing business growth. Additionally, the study recommends that efforts should be made by the government and non-governmental organizations to support entrepreneurs with free training and open access to finance for sustainable business growth in the country. Also, the government should include entrepreneurship training in the education system at the primary and secondary school levels so that learners are exposed to entrepreneurship at a young age, both in rural and urban areas. Finally, the two tertiary institutions in the country, the National University of Lesotho and Limkokwing University of Creative Technology, should introduce short-time entrepreneurship courses for potential and existing entrepreneurs who for various reasons cannot enroll for a full-time entrepreneurship degree programme.

Financial assistance should also be given to trained entrepreneurs, particularly those who have completed entrepreneurship programmes at the two universities in the country. For a start, policymakers and donor agencies can target top achievers after graduation and give them start-up financial assistance. This can gradually be extended till most, if not all, entrepreneurship graduates are financially supported. Finally, entrepreneurship education providers should engage in tracer studies so as to acquaint themselves with how their products are faring, what challenges they are encountering among others. This will go a long way for

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